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ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Profesor innovador de la nueva escuela ucraniana. Factores sociales, psicológicos y jurídicos de la actualidad docente

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Resumen. El objetivo del estudio es un análisis exhaustivo de los fundamentos teóricos, prácticos, legales, psicológicos y sociales de la actividad de un docente innovador en el contexto de la implementación del Concepto de la Nueva Escuela Ucraniana (NUS). El artículo identifica su nivel de preparación profesional para actividades educativas innovadoras, considerando la influencia del entorno social. Se formulan recomendaciones para aumentar la eficacia de la práctica pedagógica innovadora en el contexto de los desafíos sociales actuales. El estudio utiliza diversos métodos: análisis de literatura científica y normativa, enfoques sistémico-estructurales y jurídicos comparativos, generalización, síntesis, análisis lógico, así como el estudio de las condiciones sociopedagógicas para el funcionamiento del entorno educativo. Se determina que la preparación profesional de un docente innovador incluye creatividad, flexibilidad de pensamiento, liderazgo, un alto nivel de competencia digital, capacidad para la interacción en equipo y para trabajar en entornos de desigualdad social, inclusión y crisis. La base legal de la actividad docente está regulada por la legislación vigente de Ucrania, los estándares profesionales y los programas educativos que determinan sus derechos, deberes, responsabilidades y misión social. Se presta especial

atención a los aspectos psicológicos de la actividad profesional. Está comprobado que tener en cuenta los factores sociales, en particular la influencia del entorno familiar, comunitario e informativo, aumenta la eficacia de la implementación del Concepto de Escuela Nacional de Educación y contribuye a la formación de una personalidad socialmente responsable y competitiva del estudiante.

Palabras clave: responsabilidad social, cambios sociales, factores legales, preparación psicológica, profesor innovador.

Innovative teacher of the new ukrainian school. Current social, psychological, and legal factors in teaching

Abstract. The purpose of the study is a comprehensive analysis of the theoretical and practical, legal, psychological and social foundations of the activities of an innovative teacher in the context of the implementation of the Concept of the New Ukrainian School (NUS). The article identifies the levels of his professional readiness for innovative educational activities, taking into account the influence of the social environment. Recommendations are formulated to increase the effectiveness of innovative pedagogical practice in the context of modern social challenges. The study uses a set of methods: analysis of scientific and regulatory literature, system-structural and comparative legal approaches, generalization, synthesis, logical analysis, as well as the study of socio-pedagogical conditions for the functioning of the educational environment. It is determined that the professional readiness of an innovative teacher includes creativity, flexibility of thinking, leadership qualities, a high level of digital competence, the ability to team interaction and work in conditions of social inequality, inclusion and crisis transformations. The legal basis of a teacher's activities is regulated by the current legislation of Ukraine, professional standards and educational programs that determine his rights, duties, responsibility and social mission. Special attention is paid to the psychological aspects of professional activity. It is proven that taking into account social factors, in particular the influence of the family, community and information environment, increases the effectiveness of the implementation of the Concept of the National School of Education and contributes to the formation of a socially responsible, competitive personality of the student.

Keywords: social responsibility, social changes, legal factors, psychological readiness, innovative teacher.

INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the chosen topic lies in the fact that in the context of the educational system reform in Ukraine and the implementation of the Concept of the New Ukrainian School, there is a growing need to train teachers who are able to work effectively in an innovative educational environment. Innovative activity of a teacher requires not only professional competence, but also psychological readiness for changes, as well as legal knowledge regarding the

organization and innovative activity implementation. At the same time, social factors, such as educational inequality, differences in the social status of students, and the peculiarities of the socio-cultural environment, determine the need to form socially responsible pedagogical practices and create a fair and inclusive educational space.

At the same time, there is a need for systematic research into the theoretical, legal, psychological, and social foundations of teachers' innovative activities, which will ensure the high-quality implementation of the New Ukrainian School (NUS) and the formation of a modern educational space. The current Ukrainian educative reforming stage is characterized by the introduction of innovative teaching technologies, which is one of the key implementation areas of the "New Ukrainian School" Concept (Kryvylova et al., 2022). In the modern socio-cultural environment, which is rapidly changing, not only the formation of basic students' competencies becomes relevant, but also the development of their creativity, initiative, critical thinking, ability to independent learning and civic activity. At the same time, the social issues that run through educational practice determine the need to overcome educational inequality, support vulnerable students and create an inclusive, fair and safe learning environment.

Therefore, the professional teacher's growth as an innovative specialist who is able to ensure the educational process on the humanization principles, democratization, legal culture and social responsibility becomes especially important.

Innovative pedagogical activity within the framework of the National Education School involves not only the use of modern methods and technologies, but also responsible compliance with legal norms that regulate the educational process, participants' rights protection in education and creation of a safe, comfortable educational environment. In this context, the psychological conditions of the professional activity of an innovative teacher are of particular importance: the ability to be emotionally stable, professional self-esteem, empathy, effective communication with students and their parents, as well as attention to the social needs of students, support for their social adaptation, and ensuring equal inclusion in the educational process.

The theoretical justification of the problem is connected with the main ideas of the New Ukrainian School Concept, among which the key ones are the innovative support in education and the teachers' preparation for innovative activities. The implementation of these ideas requires a combination of pedagogical, psychological, legal, and social approaches, which allows to ensure the development of students' skills of independent creative thinking, the ability to solve problems in new conditions, as well as active civic position formation. In such conditions, an innovative teacher acts not only as a carrier of knowledge, but also as an organizer of the educational space, which ensures the realization of the rights of training participants to quality education, social support, and comprehensive personal development. (Oleksenko et al., 2021)

In philosophical science, activity is interpreted as an abstract concept that encompasses the socio-historical universal human practice processes. It is considered as the interaction of the subject and the object, a dialectical process that combines objectivity and subjectivity (Philosophical Encyclopedic Dictionary, 2002).

The psychological approach defines activity as the functional activity of an individual in the interactive process with the surrounding world (Psychological Dictionary, 1982). Psychologists

distinguish two activity forms: external, objective (the initial and basic form of activity) and internal, individual. These forms are interconnected and pass into each other in the development process, since they have a common structure and component composition (needs, motives, goals, tasks, actions and operations).

Analysis of philosophical, psychological and pedagogical sources allows us to formulate the following conclusions regarding the activity essence: 1) it includes three components - a subject (person), an object (reality) and the interaction processes; 2) activity is a process of realizing the subject's relations to the surrounding reality; 3) it always has a creative and independent character.

Activity can be classified according to various characteristics, for example, into spiritual and material, production and non-production, labor and non-labor. However, from the creative point of view, it is important to distinguish between reproductive activity aimed at achieving known results by known methods and productive activity associated with the creation of new goals and means of achieving them using innovative approaches (Murashchenko, 2023^a), (Murashchenko, 2023^b).

One of the productive activity varieties is innovative pedagogical activity. Analysis of its essence reveals different interpretations and definitions depending on the conceptual approach, content and researching direction. A large number of definitions emphasize the multifaceted and ambiguous natural concept.

In pedagogical literature, innovative pedagogical activity is considered in two aspects: as a process that includes the developing idea stages, mastering new knowledge and competencies, as well as implementing innovations into practice; and as a higher pedagogical creativity level and invention. Both approaches are significant for the modern education development. A systematic approach ensures the planning, development and innovation implementation, guarantees their sustainability and effectiveness. Instead, the creative approach provides teachers with freedom of thought, stimulates initiative and creativity, contributing to the search for new ideas and methods that can improve the educational process. Taken together, these perspectives complement each other, contributing to the further educative system development and improving the educative quality (Murashchenko, 2023).

In the implementation context of the NUS Concept, the activities of an innovative teacher are based on a combination with psychological and legal principles that ensure compliance with students' rights, their safety and educational innovation effectiveness. The systemic approach allows planning and implementing new methods on a scientifically sound basis, while the creative approach stimulates pedagogical initiative, creativity and the search for non-standard solutions.

Thus, the study of the psychological and legal foundations of innovative pedagogical activity becomes a key factor in the development of modern education, capable of combining efficiency, creativity, and social responsibility, ensuring equal access to quality education, forming an inclusive educational environment, and meeting the strategic guidelines for implementing the Concept of the New Ukrainian School.

Analysis of recent research and publications

In scientific research of recent years, psychological and legal foundation problem of the innovative teacher's activity is gaining particularly relevant in the implementation context of the Concept of the New Ukrainian School. Domestic and foreign scientists focus on studying the personal teacher's characteristics, professional competence, readiness for innovative activity, as well as compliance with the regulatory and legal requirements for educational process. A significant number of works are devoted to pedagogical innovation issues, professional development of the teacher, psychological support of educational changes and legal support of the teacher's activity in transformation conditions of the modern school.

In its article, Kijan O. (2024) reveals the psychological and pedagogical aspect of scientific and methodological innovative activity support of general secondary education institutions, emphasizing that innovative educational processes are aimed at updating the pedagogical process and developing the creative potential of training participants. The author notes that the introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies, new models and approaches to teaching, upbringing and management requires modern methodological support and training of a teacher who is able not only to respond to the challenges of education, but also to actively influence changes in the educational environment. Particular attention is paid to the psychological and pedagogical aspects of innovative activity, in particular, practice-oriented education, which involves the active teachers' involvement in innovations, readiness to improve professional skills, innovative thinking and self-development. Kijan also emphasizes that modern conditions require the psychological and pedagogical educational institution service to find effective ways to support teachers in the innovation implementation, since pedagogical education development determines the quality of staffing of the entire education system and must meet social demands and international trends.

O. Honcharova, (2008) considers innovative pedagogical activity as a complex integrated formation that combines various types of work in terms of goals and nature. It is aimed at introducing changes and creating something new in the professional activity system of the future teacher. Its activity is systemic, as it is aimed at implementing innovations through the use and implementation of new scientific ideas, knowledge and approaches. It may include the transformation of known scientific research and practical developing results into a new or improved product.

Hutsulyak L. (2017) reveals the concept of "socio-educational environment" and identifies three of its components: the family as a social institution, a general educational institution and a microdistrict. The author emphasizes that the creation of a favorable socio-educational environment is key to the activities of an innovative teacher in the context of the implementation of the Concept of the New Ukrainian School, since it contributes to the development of the student's personality and the ability to socially progressive self-realization. Important social factors are the cooperation of the teacher with parents, social institutions and the community, which allows overcoming the social challenges of modern society, ensuring inclusiveness, social responsibility and effective implementation of innovative approaches in the educational process.

In her article, Gladishko Y. (2025) considers the issue of forming a policy of a safe educational environment in secondary education institutions, emphasizing that ensuring safety is a key factor in the effectiveness of the educational process and social adaptation of students and teachers in a multi-level social environment. The author notes that modern social challenges, in particular the consequences of a full-scale war, increased psychological tension among participants in the educational process and social inequality among students, require the integration of not only physical security measures, but also complex psychological and social support mechanisms. Particular attention is paid to the multi-level interaction of the administration, teaching staff, students, parents and the local community to create an inclusive, safe, socially balanced and comfortable educational environment. Gladishko Y. also emphasizes the need to use innovative technologies, such as video surveillance systems, digital platforms for communication and algorithmization of emergency response processes, as well as the adaptation of international experience to Ukrainian conditions. The author proves that an effective security policy should be based on regulatory regulation and socio-psychological support for participants in the educational process, which contributes to the formation of a socially responsible and safe educational community.

Dychkivska (2012) defines innovative pedagogical activity as a special type of creative activity based on reflection and understanding of one's own pedagogical experience by comparing and studying different pedagogical approaches, methods, technologies and actions of students in order to find effective ways and means. In the innovative pedagogical activity process, teachers demonstrate readiness for changes and development of the educational process in order to achieve better results and improve the quality of pedagogical practice.

Konovalchuk (2012) interprets innovative pedagogical activity as a meta activity aimed at changing the personal structures of the subjects of innovation (needs, motives, goals, attitudes) and technological structures (forms, methods and means). Konovalchuk, I. (2012) interprets innovative pedagogical activity as a meta activity aimed at changing the personal structures of innovation subjects (needs, motives, goals, attitudes) and technological structures (forms, methods and means).

Marinovska (2007) considers the "innovative pedagogical activity" concept through the process-structural and project-implementation approach prism in the postgraduate pedagogical education system. In the process-structural approach, teachers are involved in the innovation implementation at different stages of the "life cycle" of an educational institution. The project-implementation approach provides for greater autonomy of teachers in the selection and implementation of innovative projects, which contributes to their active creative participation and professional self-improvement.

Makohon (2002) considers innovative pedagogical activity in three aspects. First, as the creation of new original techniques and holistic pedagogical concepts that change the usual perception of pedagogical phenomena and transform socio-pedagogical relations. Secondly, as highest pedagogical creativity level, which is manifested in the invention and implementation of new ideas aimed at the formation of a creative personality through a clear definition of the goal, objectives, content and innovative teaching technologies. Thirdly, as an activity to develop, search, master and apply innovations, which emphasizes the practical focus of innovative work in education.

Demidenko, (2004) defines innovative pedagogical activity as a complex multifaceted phenomenon that covers various aspects of the interaction of participants in the educational process in order to improve the quality of education. It includes a set of different types of work that belong to important stages of the development of innovative processes and are aimed at the teacher making corrections to the system of its own professional activity. Its approach emphasizes the innovative activity complexity, which requires teachers to be creative, flexible, constantly professional development and a desire for change.

In their article, O. Vasiuk et al. (2020) propose, as an educational innovation, the establishment of social services in newly created communities in Ukraine based on local schools, transforming them into comprehensive centers of social work for children and adults, families, the elderly, and persons with disabilities. These centers are envisioned to employ social educators and social workers, cultural organizers, medical social workers, and psychologists. Legal experts, economists, and other specialists may also be engaged as consultants.

Thus, the purpose of the research was a comprehensive study of the theoretical and practical, legal and psychological activity foundations of an innovative teacher, as well as the features of implementing innovative pedagogical activities in the context of implementing the Concept of the New Ukrainian School. To achieve the set goal, it was necessary to perform the following tasks: 1) to reveal the theoretical and practical foundations of the activities of an innovative teacher and determine its role in the modern educational process; 2) to analyze the legal activity foundations of an innovative teacher in Ukraine, particularly, regulatory and legal regulation and the requirements of the teacher's professional standard; 3) to clarify the psychological activity aspects of an innovative teacher, to determine the personal qualities and psychological conditions that contribute to the innovation implementation; 4) to characterize the innovative activities of a teacher in the implementing context the Concept of the New Ukrainian School, to outline the main problems and prospects for its development.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the research process, a combination of general scientific, special pedagogical-legal and socio-pedagogical methods was used, which is due to the specifics of the subject of research - the psychological, legal and social principles of the activity of an innovative teacher in the conditions of implementing the Concept of the National School of Education and overcoming the social challenges of modern society.

General scientific methods, in particular analysis, synthesis and generalization, were used to: analyze scientific approaches to the essence of the concept of "innovative teacher" and the characteristics of his activity; generalize the main provisions of the Concept of the National School of Education, determine its impact on the educational process; form conclusions and recommendations for improving pedagogical practice, taking into account social factors, such as cooperation with students, parents and the community, inclusiveness and overcoming social inequality.

Special pedagogical and legal methods ensured the comprehensiveness, completeness and objectivity of the scientific research. The comparative method allowed us to compare different

approaches to the define innovative pedagogical activity and outline the common features of an innovative teacher. The system-structural method made it possible to characterize legal regulation of innovative pedagogical activity, determine the main regulatory legal acts and requirements of the teacher's professional standard.

The method of psychological and pedagogical analysis contributed to the identification of psychological and social conditions that ensure the successful implementation of innovations, as well as the identification of barriers and ways to overcome them.

The use of these methods in conjunction contributed to obtaining substantiated results and reliable conclusions.

Using the formal-legal method, the main legal principles of the activities of an innovative teacher were analyzed, state support mechanisms for innovative initiatives and their legal boundaries were determined. Using the systematization method, intermediate and main conclusions were formulated regarding the subject of the research.

In the revealing process of the topic and objectives of the research, a number of regulatory and legal acts were used, particularly: The Constitution of Ukraine (1996), the Law of Ukraine "On Education", the Law of Ukraine "On Complete General Secondary Education", the Law of Ukraine "On Scientific and Scientific and Technical Activities", as well as regulatory documents regulating the professional standard of a teacher and the procedure for introducing innovations into the educational process, taking into account social interaction and support for vulnerable students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Theoretical and practical principles of the innovative teacher's activity

Over the past decades, a significant number of measures have been taken to update and improve the education system. Various innovations have been introduced in educational institutions: author's schools have been created, modern curricula and educational technologies have been mastered, and the latest technical means have been used. Such changes necessitate the transformation of the teacher's professional consciousness, its attitudes and value-based guidelines, as well as the active use of innovative processes that ensure the dissemination of information about the positive aspects of innovations, innovative technologies and the results of their use. In this regard, the innovative process should be considered as an activity that encompasses the creation, assimilation and dissemination of innovations that serve as a form of implementing knowledge into practical changes. It is also important to take into account the social component of innovative pedagogy, focusing on ensuring equal opportunities for all students, supporting vulnerable groups and forming an inclusive and fair educational environment.

Innovations are a universal phenomenon inherent in all spheres of social life. It is emphasized by V. Balabanov (2004), revealing the essence of the concept of "innovative culture". The author considers culture in a broad, anthropological sense - as a specifically human way of life that distinguishes man from nature. In this context, innovative culture is interpreted as

a high level of perception of new ideas, the willingness and ability of people to support and implement innovations, as a result of which a positive attitude towards innovations becomes one of the key social values (Balabanov, 2004).

At the same time, the concept of “innovation” as the introduction of something new or the process of modernization is presented in terminological dictionaries (Ohienko, 2016). In other sources, innovation is interpreted as a new phenomenon of culture (Honcharenko, 1997). From the perspective of psychology, innovation is considered as the result of creative activity aimed at developing, creating and distributing new products and technologies, as well as introducing new organizational solutions that satisfy the needs of the individual and society and cause social and other changes. In the context of studying the structural and content characteristics of a teacher’s professional activity, particularly its design skills, it is appropriate to interpret innovation as innovation and modernization, as a new formation and as a result of creative activity (Abdalyina et al, 2011).

Volkova (2009) systematized the most widespread ideas of the educational environment regarding the essence of innovation. In particular, she considers pedagogical innovation as: 1) a form of organizing innovative activity; 2) a set of new professional actions of a teacher aimed at solving current problems of upbringing and teaching; 3) changes in educational practice; 4) a multi-component process of creating, distributing and applying new tools in the field of engineering, technology, pedagogy and science. In the already mentioned terminology dictionary, innovative activity is understood more broadly, through the concept of “innovation”, which is defined as “a branch of knowledge that studies the issues of methodology and organization of innovative activity, the patterns of development and formation of innovations, change management, overcoming resistance to innovations, adaptation of business entities to them, use and dissemination of innovations and their impact on the development of society.”

Sherudylo (2019), in turn, defines innovation in the pedagogical context as a specific form of pedagogical activity and thinking aimed at organizing innovations in education field. In its opinion, the innovative process in education is a sequence of purposeful actions aimed at updating, modifying the purpose, content, organization, forms and methods of teaching and upbringing, as well as adapting the educational process to new socio-historical conditions.

Pedagogical innovation is interpreted as a specific form of pedagogical activity and way of thinking aimed at introducing innovations in education field. It can also be considered as the process of creating, implementing and disseminating something new in educational practice. The innovative process in pedagogy is a sequence of purposeful actions aimed at updating and modifying the goals, content, organizational approaches, forms and methods of teaching and upbringing, as well as adapting the educational process to new socio-historical conditions (Turkot, 2011).

In pedagogical science, the “innovative teacher” concept is interpreted not only as a specialist who owns modern methods and teaching technologies, but also as a person capable of self-understanding, self-determination in changing socio-cultural conditions, and rethinking its own professional activity. It is a teacher who considers its profession as a value, is able to form and adjust professional goals, create new educational practices and implement them in

the educational process. Tits approach is consistent with modern educational priorities aimed at developing teachers' competence for effective activities based on ethical norms and focused on innovations that are becoming increasingly widespread in the global educational space. In particular, within the framework of pedagogical innovation, the readiness of a modern teacher of a higher education institution for innovative activity is considered as a holistic, integrative characteristic of a professional, which determines his orientation towards improving his own pedagogical practice and the development of the educational organization as a whole, and is also manifested in the ability to predict further development, analyze educational situations, identify current problems and find and implement effective ways to solve them. (Ohienko, 2016)

Thus, based on the theoretical provisions considered, it can be concluded that the concept of "innovative teacher" in pedagogical science is interpreted as a specialist capable of purposeful innovation implementation, modernization of the educational process and constant professional self-development. An innovative teacher is distinguished by creativity of thinking, flexibility in choosing methods and forms of teaching, leadership qualities, as well as a high level of digital competence, which allows for the effective use of modern technologies in educational activities. It is thanks to such characteristics that the teacher becomes an active subject of innovative processes, capable not only of adapting to changes, but also of initiating them.

An innovative approach in the activities of a teacher plays a key role in the development of the educational environment, as it contributes to improving the quality of education, updating the content and technologies of teaching, forming a competitive and dynamic educational institution, and also provides equal opportunities for all students and support for vulnerable groups in the educational process, promoting integration and social justice in education.

Legal principles of the innovative teacher's activity

Modern state policy in education defines scientific and innovative activity as a key component of the country's development. The development of science and innovation is one of the capable state and a competitive economy signs, therefore, Ukraine's transition to an innovative developing model involves the modernization of all spheres, including education. Accordingly, the legal field defines the role of teachers as active subjects of the innovation process who implement scientific achievements and innovative solutions in educational practice (Aleksiichuk, 2020).

The legal innovative teacher's activity principles are based on the legislation provisions of the on education, which provides for the condition creation for the innovative activity of educational institutions and pedagogical workers. Teachers who apply innovative approaches in teaching, management and organization of the educational process act as systemic changing agent and contribute to improving the education quality. The introduction of innovative technologies in educational activities is a natural result of the new education philosophy and the public demand for high-quality, accessible and flexible learning.

Innovations in educational activities are considered as effective and productive innovations in the content, methods, means and forms of teaching and upbringing, as well as in the management system of an educational institution, the organization of the educational process and the institutional structure. Innovative activities become particularly relevant in conditions

of martial law, when teachers have to quickly respond to new challenges and implement non-standard solutions to ensure the continuity and education safety and support for participants in the educational process.

- The legislation stipulates that the activities of an innovative teacher should ensure the sustainability of the education system, fair access to education and protection of the rights of education seekers. In this context, the state supports the active innovation implementation in education field: the development of digital ecosystems and secure platforms, blended and distance learning formats, mechanisms for recognizing the results of non-formal education, professional development of teachers, mentoring and network communities of practitioners. Such measures are aimed at ensuring the quality of education, compliance with ethical standards and data protection, reducing educational inequality and building institutional capacity for recovery and development even in emergency conditions (Verbitskyi, 2025).
- The main regulatory legal acts that determine the legal foundations of the professional activities of an innovative teacher in Ukraine include the Constitution of Ukraine and modern legislation in education field. The Constitution of Ukraine (1996) enshrines the right of every citizen to education (Article 53) and establishes state guarantees for ensuring the accessibility and quality of education, which forms the legal basis for the functioning of the education system and the activities of pedagogical workers. The Law of Ukraine “On Education” (2017) defines the purpose of education, the right to obtain it (Article 3), the basic educative principles of activity (Article 6) and establishes requirements for pedagogical workers (Article 54), laying the legal foundations for professional activity and the development of innovative approaches to education.
- Within the framework of Article 54 of the Law of Ukraine “On Education” (2017), pedagogical workers have the right to advanced training and retraining, free choice of forms of education, educational programs and institutions that carry out professional development. This creates a legal mechanism for supporting innovative pedagogical activity, as it provides opportunities for constant updating of professional competencies, mastering modern methods and introducing new pedagogical technologies.
- The regulatory and legal support for innovation processes in education in Ukraine forms a holistic framework of state policy, enshrined in a number of laws and by-laws. The key documents that determine the legal basis for teachers’ innovative activities include:
 - Law of Ukraine “On Innovation Activity” (2002, as amended in 2022);
 - Law of Ukraine “On Scientific and Scientific-Technical Activity” (2016, as amended in 2022);
 - Law of Ukraine “On the National Informatization Program” (2022);
 - Regulations on the Procedure for Implementing Innovation Activity in education field (Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine dated 12.05.2023 No. 552).

Taken together, these regulatory legal acts:

- 1) establish the humanistic educative principles, focused on universal human values, national identity and academic integrity;
- 2) determine the legal, economic and organizational foundations of innovative state regulative activity;
- 3) establish tools for stimulating innovation (financial, organizational, institutional mechanisms);
- 4) regulate the procedure for initiating, examining, implementing and evaluating innovation projects in educational institutions;
- 5) are aimed at supporting the innovative economic development through educational transformations.

Particularly, importance for the legal approach formation to the innovative activity of teachers is the National Strategy for the Development of Education in Ukraine for the period until 2021 (approved by the Decree of the President of Ukraine dated 06/25/2013 No. 344/2013). Based on a state analysis in the education sector, it defined the goal, strategic directions and key tasks of the state education policy and served as a roadmap for the educative modernization system. At the sector level, the Ministry of Education and Science in Ukraine identified priority areas of innovative activity that have a legal basis and are implemented in educational institutions.

Among them:

- introduction of innovative teaching technologies;
- application of interactive methods using information and communication technologies;
- development of computer-oriented systems and teaching methods in various subjects and disciplines;
- creation and testing of the latest didactic models and technologies of profile teaching in general secondary education institutions;
- development of educational and scientific software, updated programs, textbooks, manuals and methodological materials of the new generation (including electronic ones).

The effectiveness of the implementation of legal norms regarding the innovative activities of teachers increases provided that:

- transparent selection and examination of innovations taking into account the criteria of evidence, security and equality of access;
- design of innovative projects in the form of “passports” containing the goal, expected results, quality and equality indicators, resource needs and scaling conditions;
- availability of institutional support (innovation centers, mentoring networks, teacher training systems);
- compliance with data protection policies and ensuring accessibility (in particular, the principles of universal learning design and inclusion), which guarantees pedagogical appropriateness, ethical responsibility, and controllability of technological innovations.

Thus, the legal framework for the activities of an innovative teacher in Ukraine is formed on the basis of state policy, which defines innovative activity as a key factor in the development of education and society. At the same time, they take into account the social aspects of education, including ensuring equal access for all children, supporting students from socially vulnerable groups, and combating bullying in schools. They are based on constitutional guarantees of the right to education, the principles of accessibility and quality of education, as well as on the legislative support for the professional activities of teachers, particularly their right to advanced training and professional development. The regulatory and legal field of innovative pedagogical activity is determined by both general educational laws and special acts that regulate the procedure for implementing innovations, their examination, evaluation and support. Taken together, these documents create a legal basis for the development of innovative approaches in teaching, management and organization of the educational process, contributing to improving the quality of education and adapting the education system to modern challenges, particularly in conditions of martial law. The effectiveness of the implementation of legal norms regarding innovative pedagogical activities is ensured through transparent mechanisms for selecting and evaluating innovations, the availability of institutional support for teachers (professional networks, innovation centers, advanced training programs), as well as adherence to the principles of ethics, safety, and accessibility of education, which contributes to the formation of a sustainable and competitive education system.

Psychological activity aspects of an innovative teacher

The modern system of general secondary education and society increasingly need a teacher who is able to act effectively in an innovative format, even under martial law. In this regard, in scientific research on educational innovation, special attention is focused on analyzing the role of the teacher, as well as on studying its personal, methodological and technological readiness to implement innovative activities (Kiyani, 2024).

In the psychological aspects of the innovative teacher's activity context, the psychological and pedagogical component of the scientific and methodological support of innovative activities consists in providing professional support to teachers in the supervision and interview form, as well as in organizing training seminars and trainings. It is due to the fact that innovativeness is an indicator of the professional competence and pedagogical skills of the teacher.

An important role in the psychological and pedagogical supporting system is played by non-traditional forms of work with teachers, particularly pedagogical councils, debates, trainings, business and role-playing games, seminars, workshops, co-working, professional debates, schools of pedagogical experience and methodological skills. Within the framework of these activity forms, implementing innovative pedagogical technological issues, modern methodologies, interactive methods, techniques and learning forms, scientific and research work organization, testing of scientific and methodological with educational literature, effective pedagogical experience dissemination and information about educational innovations are discussed.

Essential components are also the holding of conferences, methodological seminars and pedagogical readings, methodological support of innovative activities, encouragement of innovative teachers, creation of pedagogical conditions for the formation and application of inno-

vative technologies, competitions organization, stimulation of the pedagogical innovative use, analysis of the implementation and impact effectiveness of the educational process, as well as the presentation material distribution in electronic publications.

Researchers associate pedagogical innovations with such characteristics as expediency, progressiveness, positive orientation, modernity and prospects. The preparation of a teacher for innovative activities is considered as a holistic process of formation of the personality of a teacher who realizes the purpose of innovations, perfectly masters pedagogical techniques and achieves high performance in professional activities (Novhorodska, 2024).

In conditions of constant changes and renewal of the educational space, innovative pedagogical activities are an important factor in the professional development of a teacher. It is focused on the purposeful, harmonious and comprehensive development of the teacher's personality, as well as on the systematic improvement of its professional skills and abilities. Such activity is based on modern innovative pedagogical concepts, has a scientific basis and is implemented creatively in the educational process in order to achieve new qualitative results and increase the efficiency of education.

Theoretical analysis of research by domestic scientists on the psychological readiness of a teacher to master innovative technologies allows us to assert that the innovative teacher's activity can be transformed into an internal need and acquire a stable, sustainable character. A teacher who has a high level of psychological readiness for innovative activity not only effectively owns personally-oriented technologies, but also shows an active position in understanding innovations through the exchange of experience with colleagues, proactively participates in the creation and testing of innovations, and also experimentally confirms their effectiveness in its own professional practice (Novhorodska, 2024).

Thus, the main psychological aspect of the innovative teacher's activity is to ensure a system of support for its psychological readiness for innovative activity. This should be carried out both at the level of the administration of the educational institution and methodological offices, and at the level of institutes of postgraduate pedagogical education.

Psychological and pedagogical support for the formation of psychological readiness of an innovative teacher is understood as a holistic system of effective measures, technologies and procedures aimed at overcoming stereotypical thinking, developing personal qualities that ensure readiness for mastering innovative technologies and creative self-realization.

The main psychological and pedagogical supporting tasks for the innovative teacher's activity are:

- 1) promoting professional development and self-development of teachers, their adaptation to modern educational requirements;
- 2) forming a stable motivation for the use of innovative educational technologies in the educational process;
- 3) developing competence in the use of personality-oriented technologies in pedagogical interaction;

- 4) improving horizontal and vertical cooperation of the teaching staff in order to increase the efficiency of the use of educational technologies;
- 5) involving teachers in interactive interaction, which contributes to the development of personal qualities necessary for the creative innovation implementation;
- 6) creating conditions for coordinating scientific and psychological research on the testing of innovations in pedagogical interaction at the state and regional levels (Shevchyshena, 2018).

The administration of educational institutions and methodological offices should provide psychological support to teachers during adaptation to innovative activities by providing assistance in identifying the strengths and limitations of the personality, as well as developing recommendations taking into account the individual psychological characteristics of each teacher.

Thus, the modern system of general secondary education requires an innovative teacher who is able to act effectively in conditions of constant change and even martial law, as well as take into account social challenges, such as inequality in access to education, bullying, and the difficulties of integrating children from different social backgrounds.

Therefore scientific research focuses on the personal, methodological and technological readiness of the teacher for innovative activities; in the psychological dimension, this involves the development of such qualities as emotional intelligence, stress resistance and motivation for self-development, as well as overcoming psychological barriers (fear of failure, stereotypical thinking, insecurity) through systematic psychological and pedagogical support, which is implemented in the form of supervision, interviews, seminars, trainings, pedagogical councils, discussions, co-working, debates and other interactive forms; An important component is also pedagogical culture and communication skills, which ensure effective interaction, exchange of experience, support for innovative activities and the creation of a favorable psychological climate in the educational environment, which, in turn, contributes to the professional development of the teacher and the improvement of the quality of education.

Social factors of the innovative teacher's activity

Social factors determine the external environment and conditions in which the teacher implements innovative practices and play a key role in shaping effective educational activities. Such factors include the level of support from colleagues, school administration and parents, the presence of partnerships in the teaching staff, as well as a social climate in the classroom that promotes openness, cooperation and mutual understanding.

An important aspect is the adaptation of the educational process to the social needs of students and the community, which includes taking into account various socio-cultural conditions, the needs of children with different levels of opportunities and ensuring inclusiveness. The social responsibility of the teacher is manifested in creating a safe and supportive environment that stimulates the development of social skills, critical thinking and life competencies of students.

Therefore, social factors not only form the conditions for innovative pedagogical activity, but also determine the success of the implementation of the Concept of the New Ukrainian

School, aimed at the development of the personality, active socialization and preparation for life in modern society. (Prots, et al 2025)

Social factors of the activity of an innovative teacher are formed under the influence of socio-cultural conditions of professional activity and involve taking into account social differentiation, the characteristics of the educational environment, the educational needs of students and partnership with the community. Important components are ensuring equal opportunities for access to quality education, supporting students from socially vulnerable groups, developing an inclusive educational space and forming socially responsible behavior of education seekers. Taking into account social factors increases the effectiveness of innovative pedagogical activity, contributes to the creation of a safe and comfortable educational environment, and also ensures the comprehensive development of the student's personality in the conditions of modern social transformations.

Thus, social factors are an important component of the activities of an innovative teacher, since they determine the conditions for professional implementation and the effectiveness of introducing innovations into the educational process. Taking into account the socio-cultural environment, support from the educational community, partnership with parents and the community contributes to the formation of a favorable socio-pedagogical climate. Ensuring equal access to quality education, inclusiveness and support for socially vulnerable categories of students, which corresponds to modern educational transformations, is of particular importance. The implementation of social factors in the activities of a teacher contributes to the creation of a safe educational environment, the development of social competencies of students and their successful socialization. In the context of the Concept of the New Ukrainian School, the social aspects of innovative pedagogical activity are an important tool for ensuring the quality of education, the formation of a responsible personality and preparing students for life in modern society.

Innovative activities in the context of implementing the NUS Concept

The reform of Ukrainian education within the framework of the New Ukrainian School concept necessitates the formation of a new teacher's type who is able to act effectively in the conditions of rapid socio-cultural transformations, digitalization and the growth of the innovative pedagogical practice role. That is why innovative teacher training is built on the basis of a number of scientific paradigms that ensure the integrity, scientific validity and effectiveness of the modern professional education model of teachers (Tsurkan, 2020).

- 1) Competency-based approach. The competency-based approach is the basic methodological basis that determines the content, structure and results of teacher training in accordance with the requirements of state education standards and the professional standard "Teacher of a general secondary education institution". It orients the educational process towards the formation of the teacher's ability to act in real professional situations, applying knowledge, skills, experience and professional values. In the context of NUS, this involves the development of key and subject-specific competencies (digital, communicative, inclusive, design, methodological), autonomy, critical thinking and the ability to solve pedagogical problems, and the assessment of results is carried out through practical cases, pedagogical situations and portfolios (Marinovska, 2023).

- 2) Activity approach. The activity approach emphasizes the priority of practical activity over passive assimilation of information, which corresponds to the principles of NUS regarding active learning and the formation of competencies. It is implemented through pedagogical practice, modeling of real educational situations (simulations, trainings, cases), active learning methods (project activities, research tasks, group work, facilitation sessions) and the development of pedagogical reflection.
- 3) Person-oriented approach. This approach focuses on the humanization of pedagogical education and the development of the teacher as an active subject of professional development. In the context of the National Higher Education System, it involves creating conditions for self-realization, development of motivation and professional identity, freedom of choice of forms and methods of learning, development of empathy, communicative culture and socio-emotional competence, as well as the ability to self-regulation and self-management.
- 4) Acmeological approach. The acmeological approach is aimed at the professional growth of the future teacher and the disclosure of its potential, the formation of a high level of pedagogical culture and innovative activity. In the context of the National Higher Education System, this means the development of leadership qualities, responsibility, creativity, stress resistance, readiness for change, as well as support through mentoring and coaching (Vygovska et al, 2025).
- 5) The paradigm of digital pedagogy. Digital pedagogy is becoming an integral part of innovative teacher training at the National University of Education, as the integration of digital resources, online platforms, artificial intelligence, and media technologies is a necessary condition for the modern educational process. It involves the formation of digital literacy and digital pedagogical culture, mastery of Ed Tech tools, the organization of online, blended, and hybrid learning, as well as the design of digital educational environments.
- 6) Inclusive approach. An inclusive approach ensures the teacher's readiness to work with students with different educational needs, to create an accessible and safe environment. In the context of NUS, this involves the formation of inclusive competence, the development of differentiated methods and universal learning design, the development of teamwork and awareness of the value of diversity (Hrabovska et al, 2025).

Therefore, the psychological aspects of the activities of an innovative teacher in the implementation context of the NUS Concept consist in the formation of the teacher's professional readiness for change through the development of emotional intelligence, stress resistance and motivation for self-improvement, which allows for effective work in an innovative format even in martial law conditions. An important condition for the successful innovation implementation is overcoming psychological barriers (fear of failure, stereotypical thinking, internal resistance), which is provided by systematic psychological and pedagogical support: supervision, interviewing, trainings, seminars, as well as through the exchange of experience in the teaching staff. In addition, pedagogical culture and a high level of communication skills contribute to the creation of a favorable psychological climate, effective interaction between participants in the educational process and the active innovation implementation in educational practice which highlights the need for comprehensive psychological and legal support for a teacher's professional activities as

a condition for his stability, social responsibility, and ability to implement educational reforms in crisis social circumstances. (Hrabovska et al., 2025).

Thus, innovative activity in the implementation context of the NUS Concept is aimed at forming a new model of learning, where the teacher acts not only as a carrier of knowledge, but also as a facilitator, coach and mentor who supports the development of students' competencies, which strengthens the social significance of the teaching profession and its role as an agent of social change. The implementation of innovative approaches requires a high level of professional readiness of teachers, their ability to self-develop, adapt and use modern educational technologies, including digital ones. The successful implementation of the NUS depends on the systematic support of the teaching staff, the provision of conditions for professional growth and cooperation, as well as the active participation of teachers in the process of innovative renewal of the educational environment, which generally determines the strategic importance of psychological and legal factors in ensuring the quality and equality of modern education.

CONCLUSIONS

The theoretical foundations of the “innovative teacher” concept are understood as a pedagogical specialist who not only possesses modern knowledge, but is also able to actively introduce new methods, technologies and approaches into the educational process. In pedagogical science, an innovative teacher is interpreted as an educational changing subject, focused on student competency development, the use of digital tools and the formation of an active educational environment. The characteristic features of an innovative teacher – creativity, flexibility, leadership, digital competence – determine his ability to adapt to modern challenges, create conditions for learning that meet the needs of society, and also take into account the social aspects of education, ensuring equal opportunities for all students, supporting socially vulnerable groups and integrating students from different social backgrounds. An innovative approach in pedagogy contributes to the development of the educational environment, improves the quality of learning, activates students, ensures interactive interaction in the classroom and forms an inclusive and socially just educational environment.

The legal framework for the activities of an innovative teacher is determined by the legislative Ukrainian documents, particularly the laws “On Education” and “On Complete General Secondary Education”, which regulate the rights, obligations and pedagogical activity standards. The professional standard of a teacher emphasizes the innovative activity importance, defines the requirements for the teacher competences, particularly, the ability to apply modern educational technologies, work in a team and provide high-quality teaching. Mechanisms of legal support for innovative initiatives, such as state programs, grants, partnership projects and educational platforms, create conditions for the development of pedagogical creativity, exchange of experience and implementation of new practices in school. An important social aspect is legal support for measures aimed at overcoming social challenges, ensuring equal access to quality education and social security of participants in the educational process.

Psychological aspects of the innovative teacher's activity include the development of emotional intelligence, stress resistance and motivation for self-development, which are important

conditions for the successful implementation of changes in the educational process. Overcoming psychological barriers, such as fear of innovations, internal resistance or insecurity, ensures the effective innovation implementation and increases the teacher's readiness for professional transformations. An important component is pedagogical culture and communication skills, which contribute to high-quality interaction with students, colleagues and parents, form an atmosphere of trust, support partnerships and contribute to the creation of a socially responsible and inclusive educational environment.

Social factors play an important role in the activities of an innovative teacher, ensuring the effectiveness of the educational process and the successful implementation of the Concept of the New Ukrainian School. Taking into account the socio-cultural environment, supporting partnership with students, parents and the community contributes to the creation of an inclusive, safe and comfortable educational space. The social orientation of innovative pedagogical activity ensures equal access to education, supports socially vulnerable groups of students and contributes to their socialization and personal development

Innovative activity in the implementation NUS context the Concept is a key direction of modern education, since NUS is focused on the development of competencies, personal growth of the student, individualization of learning and the life skill formation. The main provisions of the NUS Concept require an innovative approach, which involves the implementation of active learning forms, project activities, the digital technology use, competency assessment and partnership interaction. Forms and methods of innovative activity in the educational process include interactive lessons, group projects, research tasks, facilitation, coaching, tutoring, as well as the use of digital platforms and educational resources, which necessitates the systematic study of the psychological and legal foundations of such activity as a prerequisite for ensuring the quality of education, social equality, inclusiveness, and professional sustainability of teachers in the context of modern social transformations. As a result, the innovative activity of teachers at NUS contributes to the formation of a new educational space, where the student is an active subject of learning, and the teacher is a leader of change and support.

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